

Kinetics of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Diethanolamine by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

ANIL K. AWASTHI and SANTOSH K. UPADHYAY*

Department of Chemistry, H. B. Technological Institute, Kanpur-208 002

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RECENTLY, we have reported the oxidation of some aminoalcohols by hexacyanoferrate(III)^{1,2} and cerium(IV)³ in the presence of ruthenium(III) as catalyst. The studies have shown a strong catalytic influence of ruthenium(III). The rate of uncatalysed oxidation of diethanolamine by hexacyanoferrate(III)⁴ and chloramine-T⁵ has been found to be first order dependence with respect to [oxidant]. However, in presence of ruthenium(III) chloride as catalyst, a second order dependence of rate with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) is observed. It was, therefore, interesting to study the title reaction in detail in order to understand the nature of the reaction.

Experimental

The reagent employed were diethanolamine (A.R.), $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ (AnalaR, recrystallised), NaOH (AnalaR) and $RuCl_3$ (Johnson Matthey). Other reagents used were of A.R. grade. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The solution of $RuCl_3$ was prepared by dissolving the sample in very dilute HCl. The final strength of $RuCl_3$ and HCl were kept at 9.6×10^{-3} and $16.4 \times 10^{-2} M$, respectively.

The rates were measured spectrophotometrically at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) by monitoring the absorbance due to hexacyanoferrate(III) as a function of time at 420 nm (λ_{max} of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$) on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. The concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) was kept below $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ to obey Beer's law. The absorbance due to catalyst and hexacyanoferrate(II) were negligible at the chosen wavelength.

Stoichiometry of the reaction showed that each molecule of diethanolamine consumed four molecules of hexacyanoferrate(III) in absence as well as in presence of the catalyst. The formaldehyde as the end-product was detected by spot test, in agreement with the earlier studies on uncatalysed oxidation of diethanolamine^{4,5}. (The carbon-carbon and carbon-nitrogen cleavage products resulting from the oxidation of aminoalcohols by other oxidants have also been reported^{7,8} previously). The yield of formaldehyde in the product analysis was observed as $\sim 70\%$.

Results and Discussion

The interesting feature of the reaction is the effect of hexacyanoferrate(III) on the rate of oxidation. At low initial [oxidant], the second order plots in oxidant, *i.e.* $1/(\text{absorbance})$ vs time plots were linear, whereas at higher initial concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III), the second order plots showed a initial curvature upto 10–15% of the reaction, then became linear (Fig. 1). Thus the reactions were initially rapid (upto 10–15%), then follow second order dependence of rate in

Fig 1. Second order plots at 35° , $[OH^-] = 0.1 M$, $[Diethanolamine] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ru^{III}] = 3.84 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ in a, b, c, d and e, respectively.

hexacyanoferrate(III). Therefore, the pseudo-second order rate constant (k_2) in hexacyanoferrate(III) at various initial concentrations of reactants were evaluated from the slopes of straight lines plotted between $1/(\text{absorbance})$ and time. However, an increase in the initial [oxidant] resulted in a decrease in k_2 . The results of the effect of change in concentration of diethanolamine and alkali were identical. The effect of $[OH^-]$ on the rate was studied at a fixed ionic strength ($\mu = 0.2 M NaClO_4$). The amount of NaOH required to neutralise HCl in the catalyst was taken into account. The plots of k_2 vs [substrate] or $[OH^-]$ were linear emerging from the origin and suggesting first order dependence of rate in both substrate and alkali. The plot of k_2 vs $[Ru^{III}]$ was linear with an intercept suggesting rate is proportional to ruthenium(III) and also that rate of uncatalysed path of the reaction is not negligible.

The measurements were also made at 35, 40, 45 and 50° to investigate the effect of temperature. The value of energy of activation calculated from Arrhenius plot was $\sim 41.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Ruthenium(III) chloride is known to exist as $[Ru(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$ in the hydrated form⁹. Metal ions of the form $[M(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$ are also known to exist as $[M(H_2O)_5(OH)]^{2+}$ in an alkaline medium¹⁰. Further existance of $[Ru(H_2O)_5(OH^-)]^{2+}$ species in alkaline medium is reported^{1,2,11-13}. Thus, the equilibrium (1) may be operative in alkaline media.

where, the coordinated water molecules have been omitted for the sake of simplicity. From equilibrium (1), we obtain,

$$[\text{C}_1] = K_1 [\text{Ru}^{3+}] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (2)$$

The ruthenium(III)-catalysed oxidation of alcohols^{11,12}, amines¹³ and primary aminoalcohols¹ have shown to proceed via an intermediate complex C₁ and the substrate. On the basis of above facts and the experimental results, the mechanism for ruthenium(III)-catalysed oxidation of diethanolamine may be represented as

The rate of disappearance of Fe(CN)₆³⁻ for catalysed path is given by equation (6),

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] =$$

$$2K_1 K_3 K_4 k_5 [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Ru}^{3+}] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]^2 \quad (6)$$

where, $K_3 = k_3/k_{-3}$ and $K_4 = k_4/k_{-4}$.

At higher hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations, reaction becomes complicated. Thus at lower hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration, according to above rate law equation (6), the reaction is first order in each substrate, alkali and ruthenium(III), and second order in hexacyanoferrate(III). The results are in agreement with rate law equation (6).

The plot of k_{obs} vs [Ru³⁺] gave intercept suggesting that rate of uncatalysed path is not negligible. The value of intercept could not be compared directly with rate of uncatalysed reaction reported⁴, since the uncatalysed reaction follows different kinetics, being first order in oxidant in contrast to second order dependence of rate in ruthenium(III) catalysed reaction. In this proposed mechanism for catalysed path, the steps responsible for uncatalysed reaction have also not been included, therefore, the intercept is also not reflected by rate law equation (6).

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Solvent Steric Effect and its Correlation with a Function of Solvent Mass

J. M. JESSY

Department of Chemistry, Calicut University,
Calicut-673 635

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It has been suggested¹ that the rate-retardation observed for the solvolysis of tert-butyl halides on changing the solvent through methanol, ethanol, isopropanol and tert-butanol (sterically, α-series) is likely to be due to increasing steric hindrance to solvation of the carbonium ion (or ion-pair) by the increasing bulk of the solvent molecule. In the present work, this 'solvent steric effect' is further demonstrated for a set of alcohols of normal series. Moreover, a correlation between the solvent steric effect and a function of solvent molecular weight, giving good correlation coefficients, is reported.

Experimental

The first order rate constants of the solvolyses of tert-butyl chloride were determined in n-pentanol, n-butanol, n-pentanol, n-hexanol and n-heptanol at 50°. For purification of the solvents and for determining the rate constants, methods described in literature were followed^{2,3}.

Results and Discussion

The results and all the pertinent data are given in Table 1.

The solvolysis rate is found to decrease with increasing number of methylene groups in the